

LINGUISTIC AND GRAMMATICAL ASPECTS OF WRITTEN TRANSLATION: CHALLENGES IN WORD MEANING AND SENTENCE STRUCTURE ACROSS ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract:

This paper discusses the key grammatical aspects of written translation, with a specific focus on interpreting word meanings and word combinations between English and Uzbek. It examines the typological and structural differences between the two languages and how they influence translation strategies.

Keywords:

Comparative linguistics, grammatical transformation, sentence structure, translation equivalence, personal pronouns, prepositional discrepancies.

Language systems differ by their grammatical structure and symbolic representation. For instance, English, part of the Germanic branch within the Indo-European family, exhibits an analytical morphological nature, whereas Uzbek, from the Turkic branch of the Altaic family, follows an agglutinative structure. These linguistic differences affect how words and sentences are constructed and translated.

For example:

The hunter killed the wolf. → Ovchi bo'rini o'ldirdi.
- I go to school. → Men maktabga boraman.

In English, sentence meaning heavily depends on fixed word order (S-P-O), while Uzbek allows more flexibility, typically following an S-O-P pattern. Rearranging words in English often changes the meaning entirely, whereas in Uzbek, such changes may still preserve meaning due to morphological markers like the suffix -ni.

English and Uzbek grammatical systems align in some cases and differ in others:

1. Complete grammatical equivalence – when both languages share the same grammatical function and category.

2. Partial grammatical equivalence – when categories exist in both languages but differ in form or usage (e.g., noun agreement).

3. Grammatical incompatibility – when there is no direct grammatical equivalent, such as possessive markers in Uzbek (kitobim, kitobing) versus possessive pronouns in English (my book, your book).

Additionally, English articles (a, an, the) express definiteness, while Uzbek lacks article equivalents and instead uses context or sentence structure to convey similar meanings.

Syntactic structures also reveal varying degrees of compatibility. Phrases like white flag (Adjective + Noun) translate directly to oq bayroq. However, other sentence types, such as those with impersonal or participial constructions, require deeper syntactic adjustments. For example:

I heard the door open. → Eshik ochilganini eshitdim.

To effectively translate, several grammatical transformation techniques are applied:

- Substitution – Replacing one grammatical element with another.
- Transposition – Changing the order of sentence components.
- Omission – Skipping elements unnecessary in the target language.
- Addition – Inserting elements to maintain meaning or clarity.

An example of grammatical substitution includes:

He says he will come. → U kelishini aytyapti.

He said he would come. → U kelishini aytdi.

Inversion in English, often for stylistic emphasis, requires reordering in Uzbek while maintaining meaning and tone.

Translation may also involve exchanging singular and plural forms depending on context:

money (singular) → деньги (plural, Russian) → pul (singular, Uzbek)

struggles (plural) → борьба (singular, Russian) → kurash (singular, Uzbek)

In conclusion, grammar is fundamental to accurate translation. Understanding full, partial, and incompatible grammatical features helps translators navigate challenges when rendering meaning between English and Uzbek. This analytical approach supports higher-quality translations by adapting syntax, morphology, and context.

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